

White organic light emitting devices based on a multiple-emissive-layer structure

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1. Introduction

White organic light-emitting devices (WOLEDs) have attracted considerable interest in the last decade for their applications as a large size display, a backlight for liquid crystal display, and a light source for general illumination. They have many advantages over other displays or light sources such as flexibility, design freedom, thin and light, distributed light emission, and low cost manufacturing [1-3]. In order to generate the desired white light, WOLEDs with various configurations have been proposed [4-8], such as (a) a multilayer device with blue, green, and red emission layers, (b) a doped device with a host material and blue, green, and red fluorescence dyes, (c) a single emission layer device with white emission materials, (d) excimer and exciplex emission, and (f) tandem structure [9-15]. Among these approaches, WOLEDs employing multi-emissive layer structure has advantages over other architectures in terms of efficiency and color controllability because the recombination current, singlet and triplet energy transfer and performance of each layer can be controlled by layer thickness, doping concentration and charge blocking layers. One important drawback of the WOLEDs with multi-emissive layers is the color shift with increasing voltage [16-19]. The color shift is believed to be originated from the shift of recombination zone with increasing voltage and easier formation of high energy excitons at higher voltage [20].

Recently, highly efficient WOLEDs using phosphorescent materials with incorporated heavy metal complexes have been reported [8,19]. Since fluorescent OLEDs which utilizes only the singlet excitons, phosphorescent OLEDs have proven to be potentially more efficient because they can harvest both single and triplet excitons and have the potential of reaching a maximum internal efficiency of 100%. Among all phosphorescent materials, iridium metal complexes are the most famous materials due to the relatively short lifetime of their triplet state. In this letter, we demonstrate a efficient white organic light emitting devices fabricated by the phosphorescent organic materials. The white emission Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage 1931 chromaticity coordinate (0.35, 0.33) was obtained using blue-emitting 4,4'-bis(2,2'-diphenylvinyl)-1,1'-biphenyl(DPVBi), and green-emitting (Alq3), and red emitting (CDBP-Ir(btp)2acac). We could obtain the contribution of red light by complete energy transfer from CDBP to

Ir(btp)2acac when the optimum doped concentration of Ir(btp)2acac is 2.5%.

2. Experimental

The configuration of the devices is ITO/N,N'-bis-(1-naphthyl)-N,N'-biphenyl-1,1'-biphenyl-4,4'-diamine (NPB) (20 nm)/DPVBi(20 nm)/CDBP:x Ir(btp)2acac(10 nm)/Alq3(25 nm)/BCP(5 nm)/CsF(1 nm)/Al (150 nm), x= 0.15, 2.5 and 3.0 wt%, and the corresponding devices are named Device A, Device B and Device C. NPB acted as hole transporting layer(HTL), BCP as electron transporting layer, hole blocking layer(ETL/HBL). All devices were grown onto a pre-cleaned ITO coated glass substrate with resistance of 20 Ohm/sq. The ITO coated substrates were routinely cleaned with detergent, distilled water, acetone, and 2-propanol and subsequently in ultrasonic bath. The substrates were dried in an oven at 100 °C, before treatment with UV-Ozone. After treatment UV-Ozone for 25 minutes, all organic layers were deposited in succession without breaking vacuum (10^{-6} Pa). Thermal deposition rates for organic materials, CsF and Al were 2 Å/S, 1 Å/S and 10 Å/S respectively. EL spectra and CIE coordination of the devices were measured by PR650 spectra scan spectrometer and the current-voltage-brightness characteristics were simultaneously measured by a Keithley 2400 programmable voltage-current source. All the measurements were carried out at room temperature under ambient conditions.

Fig.1 (a) Normalized EL spectrum of the device of A, B, and C.

3. Results and Discussion

The typical EL spectra of devices A-C are presented in Fig.1. It can be seen that the peaks of typical EL spectra locate at 470 and 620 nm, respectively, corresponding to the CIE coordinates of (0.35, 0.33) very close to the optimum white region of (0.33, 0.33). It also shows that the EL spectra responsible for white light emission of the device. For this device, the CIE coordinates of (0.35, 0.33) were independent on bias voltages. From the view of doping, the red light emission is from Ir(btp)2acac layer due to incomplete energy transfer. The emission peak of Ir(btp)2acac is at around 610 nm and a shoulder at 670 nm. We can find the intensity of red peak increases with increasing the concentration of Ir(btp)2acac from 1.5 to 3.5%. Hence, the intensity of emission peak at 610 and 670 nm increases as the concentration of Ir(btp)2acac increases. Fig.2 shows the luminance efficiency-voltage characteristics of devices A-C. The maximum efficiency was 1.93 cd/A, while the voltage was 9V and luminance was 375 cd/m². The luminance efficiencies are increased to the maximum and then decreased at higher voltage.

Fig.2. EL efficiency versus voltages characteristics

Fig.3 shows the normalized EL spectra of the white emission device with 2.5 wt% Ir in CDBP at different voltages. As the bias voltage increases, the more carriers recombine in DPVBi and Alq3. Hence, the emission intensity of red light decreases and the emission intensity of blue-greenish light increased by increasing the current. Thus, the saturated white emission with the CIE coordinates (0.35, 0.33) was achieved at 5V.

Fig.3 Normalized EL intensity of the device B at different voltages

4. Conclusions

In summary, we have fabricated efficient electrophosphorescent white organic light-emitting device with the structure of ITO/ NPB (20 nm/ DPVBi(20 nm)/CDBP:2.5% Ir(btp)2acac(10 nm)/Alq3(25 nm)/BCP(5 nm)/CsF(1 nm)/Al (150 nm) exhibiting a maximum luminance of 7005 cd/m² and efficiency 1.93 cd/A are archived at 14V and 9V respectively. The CIE coordinates of the devices vary from (0.35,0.33) at 5V to (0.26,0.33)V and are well within the white region.

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